

Monastery of Saint Nicholas of Philanthropeni

also known as “Spanos Monastery”, “St. Nicholas Monastery”, “Philanthropene Monastery”

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Entry tags: Christianity, Christian, Greece, Christianity, Religious Group, Abrahamic, Church, Monastery, Church, Greek, Language, Religious Place, Orthodoxy, Epirus, Orthodox Christianity, Balkans, Orthodoxy

Philanthropene monastery is located on the Ioannina Island. Built on the 13th century is still active, having an excellent Byzantine decoration of the 16th century. The monastery is dedicated to Saint Nicholas of Myra.

Date Range: 1292 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Ioannina Island

Region tags: Greece

Philanthropene Monastery is on the Ioannina Island in lake Pamvotis

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

The society in which the religious place is located is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Saint Nicholas and the Holy Trinity

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Holy Trinity

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Were the structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Priests

– Men

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

- ↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:
 - Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

- Thanksgiving to a god/gods for favor received

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

- Yes

- ↳ Were the scriptures/sacred texts located in a specific room within the main structure:
 - Yes

- ↳ Space underneath the structure
 - No

- ↳ Other:
 - Other [specify]: In the altar

- ↳ In the cella:

The cella refers to the most interior area of the structure, often where the cult statue(s) might be located.

 - No

- ↳ In a restricted section of the structure removed from general traffic:

This would be a back-room or remote part of the structure, i.e. Opisthodomoi in Greek temples, etc

 - Yes

Notes: The altar

- ↳ What type of scriptures/sacred texts [specify]:
 - Type: New Testament

- ↳ Where are the scriptures/sacred texts located in secondary building:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Are the scriptures actively used at the place:
 - Yes

↳ Other:
– Other [specify]: Read every Sunday

↳ Are they studied:
– Yes

↳ Are they recopied:
– Yes

↳ Used for divination:
– No

↳ Are they read aloud:
– Yes

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation
- Tree, grove, or forest

↳ Type of elevation
– Hill

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

- No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

- Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:
– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:
– Yes

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Plantings

– Clearing

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Garidis, Miltos. Μεταβυζαντινή Ζωγραφική (1450-1600). Η Εντοίχια Ζωγραφική Μετά Τη Πτώση Του Βυζαντίου Στον Ορθόδοξο Κόσμο Και Στις Χώρες Υπό Ξένη Κυριαρχία. Athens: Spanos, 207AD.

– Source 2: Acheimastou-Potamianou, Myrtali. Οι Τοιχογραφίες Της Μονής Των Φιλανθρωπηγών Στο Νησί Των Ιωαννίνων. Athens: Adam, 2004.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Restoration of the Catholicon

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1963-1974

Has this place been looted:

– No

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 Description: A description of the monument by the Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs of Greece
- Source 2 URL: http://odysseus.culture.gr/h/2/gh251.jsp?obj_id=1504
- Source 1 URL: <https://epigrepirus.project.uoi.gr/index.php/en/philanthropene-monastery>
- Source 2 Description: A description of the monument by the Ministry of Culture of Greece

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Mound

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The monasteries of Ioannina Island

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Once

Notes: Not in antiquity

↳ In modernity

–(European) Post-Renaissance

–Other (date-range):: 1963-1974

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Bricks

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 10

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 70

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 100

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Sand
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– Yes

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Lime

– I don't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No other

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Dates

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Decoration with tiles

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Secular figures of Ancient Greek Philosophers

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: A collective portrait of the family of Philanthropenoi in front of Saint Nicholas

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features of the iconography:

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: Tortures
- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - Yes
- ↳ Humans
 - Yes
- ↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - Yes
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - Yes
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
 - Yes

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Supernatural Beings

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Is a supreme high god present:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Do they have another type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Yes

Notes: Bless them

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

↳ Do they have kin relation with elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ other:

–Other [specify]: No other

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– I don't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: Through prayer

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: No other

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: No other

↳ Libations:

– No

↳ Offerings of food:

–Yes [specify]: Bread, wine, olive oil

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– No

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

↳ Sacred objects:

–Yes [specify]: Candles

↳ Daily life objects:

–Yes [specify]: Candles

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 50

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Daily

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Wine

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Notes: Bloodless sacrifice during the Divine Liturgy

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

Institutions and Scriptures

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Religious Specialists

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– No

Bureaucracy

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– No

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– Yes

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Monastery of Saint Nicholas of Philanthropeni, Acheimastou-Potamianou, Myrtali. Οι Τοιχογραφίες Της Μονής Των Φιλανθρωπηνών Στο Νησί Των Ιωαννίνων. Athens: Adam, 2004.

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